

Project information for the Kindergarten

The breathing friend. A soft robot to increase children's social security.

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Project description:

The aim of the project is to investigate the design of a soft robot that can alleviate anxiety symptoms and create a safe space for children in social situations. The robot has a design with a soft outer layer of silicone and a visual design that invites children to seek physical contact with the robot during or after anxiety-provoking situations. The robot interacts using slow breathing movements when hugged. In addition, the robot has small moving ears that make it more lifelike.

We want to investigate whether children want to use a soft robot with soothing movements when they experience insecurity.

Plan for presenting the robot to children:

The robot is presented to the children in two sessions spread over two days. The presentation will be for 3-5 of the oldest children in kindergarten. The same children attend both sessions.

A pedagogue will be present during both sessions to whom the children can rely on and get help in case they needed to.

1st session (1st day)

In this session the children are together and can interact freely with each other. The session is videotaped.

Plan:

- Introduce the researcher and the project to the children. (Estimated 10 minutes)
- Introduce the robot to the small group of children (3-5 children) together. (Estimated 20-30 minutes)
 - o Common discussion about the appearance of the robot.
 - o Opportunity for the children to become familiar with the robot by touching, holding and interacting with the robot.

Goal:

Getting to know the children and introducing the project so that it is possible to take the focus off me and put the focus on the robot in the future.

At the introduction of the robot, a qualitative insight into the first-hand impression of the robot is desired, as well as elaborating on which functions of the robot the children like.

2nd session (2nd day)

In this session, each child is alone inside the robot (In the company of a researcher and a pedagogue). The session is videotaped.

Plan:

- The child gets the opportunity to play freely and interact with the robot (Estimated 5 minutes)
- Through focused play and imagined scenarios, the children are asked questions about the appearance and use of the robot. (Estimated 10 minutes)

Goal:

When playing freely with the robot, the goal is to collect data on how the child interacts with the robot depending on how the child uses and holds the robot.

Through imagined scenarios, an understanding of how the children could see themselves using the robot is desired.

Ethical considerations:

The children have the opportunity to withdraw from the presentation at any time if they do not wish to participate. In addition, a pedagogue is requested to be present during both sessions who can help assess whether a child wishes to withdraw, as well as act as a familiar person the child can turn to if the child does not want to interact with the researcher. At NO time do we expose the children to any type of proven unsafe or anxiety-provoking situation - presentation is solely for exploring how the children could see themselves using the robot if they feel unsafe, as well as their opinions about the appearance and functions of the robot. The robot's soft material and passive movements make it safe for children. The robot has no verbal communication and thus cannot influence the children.

Data collection and data storage:

Both sessions are videorecorded. If video clips or images from the video are used in a report or publication the data will be anonymised. In addition, general personal data is collected in the form of: Age, Gender. All collected data are used exclusively for research and are collected and processed in compliance with the [GDPR](#). Only we have access to the data and can process it. The information will be deleted or anonymized, and this will happen no later than five years after the end of the project. By agreeing to participate, we will collect the information mentioned above and use it in the project. Should you, at some point in the process, no longer want your child to participate, you can withdraw your child from the project. This means that we will no longer collect new information about your child, but we have continued permission to use the information we have already obtained.

Informed consent:

Project title: The breathing friend. A soft robot to increase children's social security.

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Please read all the sections of the "Project Information for the Kindergarten" document and sign at the bottom of this page to consent to your child's participation in the above project.

- I have read and understood the "Project Information for the Kindergarten" for the above project.
- I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and get satisfactory answers on these.
- I understand that my child's participation is voluntary and that I/the child can withdraw at any time from participation in the sessions without any reason and without any negative consequence.
- I understand that the anonymized results of this project may be used in research and in published articles.

I, (name in block letters)

want my child, (name in block letters)

to participate in the project and hereby gives consent for participation.

Signature from consent giver

Date

Signature of consent recipient

Date

Consent recipient's name in block letters
